

THE SIGNIFICANCE AND EFFECTIVENESS OF USING MODERN EDUCATIONAL METHODS OF TEACHING NURSES ON VIRAL HEPATITIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14023482>

Abstract. *This article will explore the benefits and application of the law of didactic method and the following paragraphs will discuss this in the form of research.*

Keywords: *secondary education, system-structural approach, educational content, complex system, educational activities, pedagogical processes.*

Importance. Each science defines the laws of studying objective reality. Didactic laws are studied in the unity of teaching and learning and their interrelationship. When looking at the educational process in higher and secondary special educational institutions from the point of view of a system-structural approach, its two interconnected systems apply.

First, the educational process is manifested as a complex system consisting of its educational goal, educational and upbringing activities, educational content, educational tools, and modern teaching methods in the educational process. They are connected to each other.

Secondly, the educational process is a subsystem of the pedagogical process, which is a relatively large system. This system is manifested as a unit of the teaching, training and education process. At the same time, this system has a system of social processes and requirements that directly affect the laws of development of the educational process of the educational institution.

Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish between large external and internal dependence of the study wound. Based on this, views are classified. Among the components of the didactics that can grow qualitatively according to their own strength, it is possible to keep the necessary, recycled and renewable things. For this, it is necessary to move from the scientific description of the main study to its project, that is, to the one obtained from the catch.

How can knowledge laws be used in the learning process? For this, it is necessary to follow didactic principles.

Didactic principles. It is a methodological reflection of perceived didactic laws; this is knowledge about the purpose, essence, content, and structure of teaching in a form that does not prevent its use as a permanent standard of practice. So, the system of didactic principles that participate as the basic rules necessary for the organization and planning of the educational process corresponds to the system of didactic laws of the theory of teaching in the higher school. Didactic principles were developed by V.I. Zagvyazinsky, L.I. Gritsenko, M.A. Danilov, I.I. Koblyatsky, M.G. Garunov.

In substantiating the principles of teaching, higher school didactics provides for the following:

- the purpose of education that meets the requirements of society;
- Objective laws of teaching;
- Concrete conditions of the educational process.

There are different approaches to justifying the teaching principles of higher school didactics. They are as follows:

Bringing educational work closer to scientific work;

To ensure high activity of students in independent learning and cognitive activities.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above:

although the main didactic principles are common to school and higher school, their implementation is different in school and higher school.

There are also special principles that apply in the context of higher education.

Thus, in creating a system of didactic principles of a higher school, it is necessary to take into account the general laws of teaching, as well as the rules of the theory of teaching in general.

In the secondary special education system, using not the usual, but modern interactive teaching methods, involving the pupil or student in practical training, using interactive methods that match the subject of the lesson during the training is one of the main requirements of today.

Therefore, our main goal is to solve the problem of relevance of conducting practical training for students in the training of nurses in various forms of interactive methods, increasing the student's activity in the lesson process.

Purpose of the study. Achieving the importance and effectiveness of using modern teaching methods in teaching nursing care in viral hepatitis.

Research objectives:

1. The use of interactive methods in teaching nursing care in viral hepatitis.
2. Increasing the activity of students during the teaching process.
3. As a result of teaching with the help of interactive methods, the students' level of knowledge will be further strengthened.

Research results. 4 groups used the usual teaching method and 4 other groups used interactive methods of teaching. In this case, the purpose of the lesson, the tasks that the student should know, were explained by the teacher in the regular training sessions, and the students' knowledge was evaluated by asking them in the next session. In the classes conducted in the interactive method, the lesson process was carried out by involving the students in various interactive teaching methods. For this, if we consider the example of the practical exercise "Nursing care in viral hepatitis", the interactive method "Role-playing" was used with the participation of students for the purpose of "Patient's complaint, collection of anamnesis, assessment of patient's condition". In this, one of the students plays the role of "Patient" and the other "Nurse" and tells how viral hepatitis started, with whom he communicated, what clinical signs were observed, and his complaints during the examination, provides clarifications to accurately diagnose the disease. In this place, the deficiencies made by the students are filled by the teacher.

In the part of the training on "Determining grass pigments in urine" that the student should know, the same interactive method of "Role playing" was used as above.

In the final part of the training, in order to assess the students' level of mastery, that is, their knowledge, using the "Chamomile" method, pre-prepared disease-related and non-disease-related clinical signs are distributed to the students. Students collect the leaves of "Chamomile" by summarizing the clinical signs characteristic of viral hepatitis. The student evaluates another student's knowledge by checking that the collected clinical signs are correctly gathered.

Conclusion:

1. Intensive use of interactive methods in practical training caused students to master the subject quickly and thoroughly.
2. It was found that students actively participated in the practical training compared to regular training.
3. The level of knowledge of students was positively evaluated compared to regular teaching.

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